

The logo for ICCM24 is a large purple circle containing the text "ICCM24" in white, with "AUG 4-8, 2025 · BALTIMORE" below it. This circle is part of a network diagram consisting of several smaller purple circles of varying sizes connected by thin black lines. The background of the slide is a gradient from purple to blue.

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Flow analysis of the capillary-driven underfill process for the use of thermally conductive epoxy composites in semiconductor packaging

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Semiconductor packaging

❖ What is a semiconductor package?

The semiconductor package is a protective casing that connects the chip to the board/other chips and can help with heat dissipation

Semiconductor Package

• Conventional Package

• Advanced Package

Thinner, stacked chips

Heat

Durability

Underfill Material

Semiconductor packaging

❖ Underfill Material

- Composite material of epoxy and filler material that goes between the chip and substrate, improving the reliability of electrical devices.

Underfill

Filler

Epoxy

Key effect of Underfill [1]

- Mechanical Protection

- Solder bump protection
- Stress concentration mitigation

- Heat Dissipation

- Effective dissipation of heat generated by chip

Semiconductor packaging

❖ Types of Underfill Process^[2,3]

No Flow Underfill

- Fast and simplified process
- High likelihood of void formation

Molded Underfill

- Fast process time
- High cost
- High likelihood of void formation

Capillary Underfill

- Simplest process
- Cost-effectiveness
- Slow process time

Semiconductor packaging

Advanced technology in semiconductor packaging

Requirements of the capillary underfill process

No void

Reducing filling time

Void Formation

Micro-voids^[4,5]

- Micro-voids formed by interaction between bumps and flow front

Macro-voids^[6,7]

- Macro-voids formed by faster flow in the edge regions and subsequent flow front merging

Void formation

Race-tracking^[7]

- Air entrapment due to flow difference between the edge and the center

Different dispensing types and contact angles^[8]

Void formation by flow front merging

Void formation by variation in contact angles

- Void formation for different dispensing types
- Different wetting behavior (contact angles) due to flux residues

Analytic expressions of the filling time

Capillary driven flow between two plates^[9]

Assumptions

1. Incompressible
2. 2D fully-developed laminar
3. Gravity neglected

Plane Poiseuille flow

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \mu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2}$$

Young-Laplace equation for surface tension:

$$\Delta p_\sigma = \frac{2\sigma \cos\theta}{h}$$

$$t_f = \frac{6\mu x_f^2}{\Delta p_\sigma h^2} = \frac{3\mu x_f^2}{h\sigma \cos\theta}$$

t_f : filling time, x_f : flow distance

Capillary driven flow with solder bump^[10]

Pressure difference

h : gap height

$$\Delta p = \Delta p_\sigma - \Delta p_j$$

Δp_σ : pressure due to surface tension;

$$\Delta p_\sigma = \frac{2\sigma \cos\theta}{h}$$

Δp_j : pressure loss due to solder bump;

$$\Delta p_j = 2\sigma \cos\theta \left[\left(\frac{1}{h} + \frac{1}{W} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{h} + \frac{1}{W+d} \right) \right]$$

$$t_f = \frac{3\mu W(W+d)}{h\sigma \cos\theta (W^2 + dW - dh)} x_f^2$$

Experiments for flow front visualization

Scale-up experiments [11,12]

- ✓ Scale-up experiments to visualize flow front progression and calculate infiltration time
- ✓ The effects of gravity are ignored and flow similarity is not ensured

Effect of gravity [13,14]

$$Bo = \frac{\text{Gravity force}}{\text{Capillary force}}$$

- ✓ The interface changes due to the effects of gravity
- ✓ The shape of the meniscus varies depending on the gap height
- ✓ **Bond number** is a key dimensionless number

Research motivation

❖ Overview

1. In the capillary underfill process, macro-voids develop due to the merging of **flow fronts advancing at different velocities**
2. Non-uniform flow between the edge and center are recognized as factors contributing to void formation, however, the **void formation mechanism has not been extensively studied**
3. Scaled-up experiments for visualizing flow and predicting infiltration time have been conducted, however, **gravity effects and flow similarity were not considered**

Research Objectives

- Investigate the void formation mechanism both numerically and experimentally
- Optimize the capillary underfill process to minimize the filling time and void formation

Flow simulation

- Experimental validation
- Parametric study

Experiment

- Experimental design
- Flow front measurement

Flow analysis

- Velocity difference of edge and bumps
- Void formation mechanism

MODELLING & EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

- **Numerical simulation model**
- **Experiment design**

Numerical analysis

❖ Flow simulation

▪ Boundary condition

▪ Geometry

(unit: mm)

Chip size	Pitch size (W)	Bump diameter (d)	Gap height (h)
5	4.5	3	1

▪ Fluid properties (YD-114, KUKDO, Korea)

Viscosity	Density	Surface tension coefficient	Contact angle	Bump contact angle
0.6 Pa·s	1136.58 kg/m ³	0.0297 N/m	33.035°	45.939°

▪ Model

Transient flow

Multiphase flow: Volume of Fluid

Experiment design

❖ Similarity analysis

Scale up for visualization of flow

Actual chip

Scaled-up replica of chip

Chip size	Bump diameter	Bump height	Bump pitch
2.5 × 2.5	0.05	0.05	0.1

(unit: mm)

Dimensional analysis

Maintain similarity between the actual chip and scaled-up chip replica

Capillary number

$$Ca = \frac{v\mu}{\sigma}$$

Bond number

$$Bo = \frac{\rho gh^2}{\sigma}$$

μ : viscosity, ρ : density, h : gap height,
 g : gravitational acceleration, σ : surface tension

Chip size	Bump diameter	Bump height	Bump pitch
5 × 5	3	1	4.5

(unit: mm)

Experiment design

❖ Effect of gravity vs capillary

Bond number^[13,14]

$$Bo = \frac{\text{Gravity force}}{\text{Capillary force}} = \frac{\Delta\rho gh^2}{\sigma}$$

$Bo \ll 1$

$Bo \gg 1$

Analytical model

Assumptions

1. Incompressible
2. 2D fully-developed laminar
3. Gravity neglected

$$t_f = \frac{3\mu x_f^2}{h\sigma\cos\theta}$$

Experiment

- Two flat plate experiments were conducted with different gap heights
- Acrylic was used for the top and bottom plates

(unit: mm)

Height (h)	1.7	1.22	1	0.9
Bond number (Bo)	1.09	0.56	0.38	0.30

Results & Discussion

❖ Two flat plate experiment

$h = 1.7 \text{ mm}$ ($Bo = 1.09$)

$h = 1.2 \text{ mm}$ ($Bo = 0.56$)

$h = 1.0 \text{ mm}$ ($Bo = 0.38$)

$h = 0.9 \text{ mm}$ ($Bo = 0.30$)

- As the gap height decreases, Bond number becomes smaller and the effect of gravity is minimized

Experiment design

❖ Experiment design

Dimensions

Top view

Side view

(unit: mm)

Chip size (L)	Bump pitch (w)	Diameter (d)	Height (h)
5 × 5	4.5	3	1

Materials

Chip	Substrate	Ball
Acrylic (PMMA, arystal, Korea)	Acrylic (PMMA, arystal, Korea)	Bearing steel (SUJ2)

Experiment design

❖ Experiment design for original model

Applying adhesive

Attaching solderball

Attaching upper plate

Experiment design

❖ Flow front measurement

❖ Flow front measurement method

- Measurement tool: Image correlation
- 5 mm \rightarrow 41 pixel
- Time step: 10 s

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

- **Simulation & experimental results**
- **Void formation mechanism**
- **Parametric study**

Experimental validation

Experiment

Simulation

Experimental validation

❖ Scale-up model

Experimental validation

❖ Original scale model

Experimental validation

❖ Flow similarity between scale-up and original scale models

Parametric study

Representative model for parametric study

3 × 3 solderball model

Model	Bump pitch (W)	(unit: μm)
		Gap height (h)
1		25
2	100	40
3		60
4		30
5	120	55
6		80
7		40
8	140	70
9		100

Parametric study

Model	Bump pitch (μm)	Gap height (μm)
1		25
2	100	40
3		60
4		30
5	120	55
6		80
7		40
8	140	70
9		100

Void formation mechanism

Bump pitch effect

- ✓ As the bump pitch decreases, the pressure drop across the bumps and the viscous drag increase \Rightarrow decreased flow velocity in bump region
- ✓ Difference between the flow in the edge and bump regions increases the amount of transverse flow.

Gap height effect

Flow direction

$$P_L = 2\sigma\cos\theta\frac{1}{h}$$

Transverse flow direction

$$P_T = 2\sigma\cos\theta\left(\frac{1}{h} + \frac{1}{w}\right)$$

- ✓ As the gap height becomes larger, the effect of the transverse capillary force increases.

Void formation mechanism

Flow front direction change

Simulation results of void formation

Parametric study

Model	Bump pitch (μm)	Gap height (μm)
10	100	15

h : gap height, w : bump clearance, d : bump diameter

CONCLUSIONS

Conclusions

- Scaled-up test bench was constructed for improved visualization of the flip chip capillary underfill process while maintaining flow similarity
- The primary cause for void formation is air entrapment due to the velocity difference between the edge and bump regions
- Flow in the solder bump region depends on both the viscous drag and pressure drop as the flow front passes through the solder bumps
- A parametric study showed that increasing gap height and decreasing bump pitch increase the likelihood of void formation

Future work

- Extend test bench to track filler particles during filling
- Simulation of the flow of the underfill material with filler particles
- ML-driven framework to predict filling patterns for complex bump arrangements and varying fluid properties

THANK YOU FOR
YOUR ATTENTION

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